

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: dos Santos****FIRST NAME: Marcelo****PROGRAM CODE : MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10.

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-7)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
4. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)

PERIOD ONE COURSEPACK

1) INTRODUCTION

For many years I worked in international companies whose English was the official language used, and therefore, I used English to communicate both writing and verbally. In one of my jobs, I worked making register of medical products and to be more specific, to register reagents to be used in medical laboratory instruments. The job consisted of translate the leaflet of these reagents and deeply understand how it works and in addition to test them inside our laboratory and check about accurate and precision during essay. After these tests the we sent reports to Health Ministry to do so perform the final process to register the product. Was really a challenger job because English is not my native language and it helps me a lot to improve my language skills. When I started to study the course pack, a lot of doubts were clear and this material bring me a route that would let my way easy and well organized. This is my first response paper (RP) and I want to prepare it and give my best because it is just starting and it will help me in the next (RP) to flow better. All the material together with other researches makes me perform a perfect work.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

In this first chapter of the coursepack, I found a brief explanation of the basic pronouncements that must be considered when writing an academic essay, as well as the most important points that need to be observed to make this process easier and meaningful when reading by somebody.(Redman and Maples, n.d.)

We need to understand what we write about and start looking for material on the subject. The more information we have, better will be our RP because much more topics will be inserted and discussed in order to enrich it. We must do a lot of research and make notes that will be useful when we start organizing our ideas. We must have the introduction, the body and the conclusion. In the introduction we will talk about the main point of our essay, in the body we will discuss and give the necessary explanations and the methodology we used in our research, and, in the conclusion, we will give the answer, that is, we will explain the result of our research. Obviously, this is a very simple explanation about the structure, however, this is the key to achieving a good RP. Finally, we will quote the references, make edits if necessary and our RP will be ready to be read and evaluated (EUCLID 2019, 2-4).

3) PLAGIARISM

The Latin word “plagiare” refers to the act of kidnapping (Das and Panjabi 2011). Plagiarism refers to the act of writing something that was write before for someone and appropriate of this content without reference the author or claiming that you are the owner of this idea (Parija and Kate, n.d., 178). When we write an essay, we must avoid plagiarism. It is not good and not ethical appropriate by ideas for other and tell that is your own. You need to give credit to the author when you use some informations that were wrote for someone. If you do not mention it in your paper, it can be considered a serious academic offense. To avoid plagiarism only need to cite the author or source. It can be result in punish and can be considered copyright violations and sanctions can be applied (Parija and Kate, n.d., 182).

4) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2019, 24). In publishing houses, the use of a style guide is a norm. However, they can also be useful for any group that works on drafting documents. A style guide is a point of reference that defines the standards for writing documents. Its focus is generally not on a question of correct or incorrect grammar, but rather to provide guidance for cases where there are many possibilities for writing (Weber, n.d.). Style guides offers the opportunity to present your brand consistently. They help to ensure that several authors use the same "tone" and help to save time and resources, providing an instant answer when doubts arise about the preferred style. The key to a good style guide is brevity. The authors use a guide as a resource and therefore it must be written following these rules, however, this guide does not work alone and must be accompanied by a specific guide depending on the area in which it will be used.

5) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

The differences between American English (US) and British English (GB) can be subdivided into different categories: pronunciation, spelling, grammar and vocabulary.

Differences in spelling: Regarding the spelling (set of rules that define the correct way of writing) of the English language, it is possible to establish a certain pattern between the differences (“British English and American English,” n.d.).

i. Terminations -se and -ce:

US: defense, license, practise

GB: defence, licence, practice

ii. Terminations -er and -re:

US: center, meter, liter, theater

GB: centre, metre, litre, theatre

iii. Sequencies -or and -our:

US: color, favorite, neighbor

GB: colour, favourite, neighbour

Differences between grammar in US and GB: One of the differences between American and British grammar is related to the verbal agreement of the sentences. In British for example, when we refer to a group, we can make the agreement in the singular or in the plural, however, in American grammar only the agreement in the singular is correct. Example:

US: Brazil was the World Cup Champion in 2002.

GB: Brazil was the World Cup Champion in 2002 or Brazil were the World Cup Champion in 2002.

Present Perfect Use: Another difference between the two language variants has to do with the use of the present perfect.

In the US, this tense is used to refer to an action that occurs in the recent past and extends to the present. In GB it is often used in place of simple past.

Furthermore, in British English, this tense is commonly used with adverbs.

In phrases like "already, just or yet", the GB usually use the present perfect and US, the simple past. Example:

US: I already saw this movie.

GB: I have already seen this movie.

Differences between Vocabulary:

American	British
TV program	TV programme
Apartment	Flat / Apartment
Movie	Film
Movie Theater	Cinema
Closet	Wardrobe
Pants	Trousers
Jail	Prison
Gas / Gasoline	Petrol
Subway	Underground
Chips	Crisps

Differences between pronunciation: One of the most pronounced differences between the two main variants of the English language is the peculiarities of the British and American accents.

The pronunciation of some specific letters tends to characterize the variants. The letter T that occurs in the middle of the word is an example of this. While in British English it is pronounced / t /, in American English it has a sound similar to / r /, that is, in the case of the word water, notice how each country is pronounced:

GB: / uotar /

US: / uorar /

6) LATIN TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Although Latin is no longer the international language of scholars, fragments of it can still be found scattered. Some of these words or abbreviations are common and even seen in academic texts while others are more obscure. The simple fact of knowing what an abbreviation stands for and how to translate Latin words does not necessarily tell the real meaning of how that abbreviation is used in modern practice. There are some generally accepted rules that apply to most Latin abbreviations. The main style manuals (MLA, APA and Chicago) agree that Latin abbreviations should be kept outside the main body of a text, it means, they should not appear in common sentences within common paragraphs. Certain abbreviations can be used within the body of a text (etc., e.g.), but the rest must appear only in notes, tables, and other forms of documentation. A notable exception: the APA style allows writers to use the abbreviation “et al.” when discussing works with several authors and “v.” in the titles of judicial proceedings. Except for “N.B.”, none of the abbreviations need to be in Italic or capital letters (“Latin-Terms-and-Abbreviations-The-Writing-Center.Pdf” n.d., 1).

7) CONCLUSION

This first response paper was a challenge for me because is my first RP in my life and was really interesting for me to check about a lot of new rules and new knowledges. I hope I can reach my target that was make a quality RP.

REFERENCES

- Redman, Peter, and Wendy Maples. n.d. *Good Essays Writing: A Social Sciences Guide*.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
- Das, Natasha, and Monica Panjabi. 2011. "Plagiarism: Why Is It Such a Big Issue for Medical Writers?" *Perspectives in Clinical Research 2*.
- Parija, Subhash C, and Viktam Kate. n.d. *Writing and Publishing a Scientific Research Paper*.
- Weber, Jean Hollis. n.d. *Writing a Style Guide: What You Need to Know*.
- British English and American English – British Council.
<https://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/grammar/intermediate-to-upper-intermediate/british-english-and-american-english>
- Latin Terms and Abbreviations – The writing Center. <https://writingcenter.unc.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/346/2012/09/Latin-Terms-and-Abbreviations-The-Writing-Center.pdf>
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.